

STEAM EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY AND DESIGN

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Abstract. *This article is about the process of modernization of educational stages in our Republic based on innovative approaches. It also provides information about the great attention paid to ensuring interdisciplinary integration aimed at forming the natural and scientific literacy of primary school students, and the introduction of STEAM - educational technology, which is focused on practical research activities.*

Keywords: *concept, program, education, normative and methodological framework, design, competency-based approach.*

INTRODUCTION

The process of modernization of educational stages in our republic is being organized on the basis of innovative approaches. Also, great attention is paid to ensuring interdisciplinary integration aimed at forming the natural and scientific literacy of primary school students, and the introduction of STEAM - educational technology, which is focused on practical research activities. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5712 dated April 29, 2019 “On Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Public Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030” places special emphasis on the development of “STEAM disciplines and the competencies and skills of critical thinking, independent processing and analysis of information. According to it, tasks such as “implementing general education programs and new state educational standards that meet the requirements of a modern innovative economy” are clearly defined. At the same time, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4623 “On measures for the further development of the sphere of pedagogical education” dated February 27, 2020 set the task of developing general secondary education based on national pedagogical experience and international educational programs. The introduction of STEAM educational technology, designed to work with tasks that meet the requirements of international assessment programs (PIRLS, PISA, TIMSS, EGMA, EGRA), into primary education, in particular, into the teaching of natural sciences, requires improving the model and methodological conditions for implementing this process.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Issues of education and upbringing of children of primary school age according to the Concept for the Development of the Primary Education System until 2030 and the National Curriculum.

The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019 No. PF - 5712 “On Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Primary Education System until 2030” was adopted.

The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 8, 2019 No. PF - 5847 “On Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System until 2030” was adopted.

When studying STEAM educational technology and the design process, it is first of all advisable to study the essence of the concepts of design and project management.

A project is a product of an effort aimed at developing the content of pedagogical activity based on a clear plan and goal, guaranteeing its results. It is manifested in the form of a program, model, technological map, etc. The basis of the project is an idea of a scientific or creative nature.

Design is a practical effort aimed at developing the content of an activity or process by estimating, predicting, and planning the expected result based on initial data. Design is based on the system of “idea - goal - expected result - estimation - prediction - planning”. Design is carried out using various resources, that is, material objects, tools, for example: computer technology, *vatmon* or ordinary working paper, ruler, pencil, marker, copier (printer) and other resource.

Design is the process of creating and drawing projects for the construction and creation of intended objects (hardware and devices, buildings and structures, roads and bridges, machines and equipment, aircraft and spacecraft, radios and televisions, telephones and computers, new types and models of clothing and footwear, furniture and other various products). It is used in all areas of science and technology. It includes the activities of economic and technical calculations, estimates, drawing and reproduction of drawings, often based on drawings, a model of an object (building, machine, etc.) is prepared.

A project is an idea, a plan, an intention, or a goal to do something.

RESULTS

In a general sense, a project is a specific plan developed to do something. Projects can be specific, for example, a set of documents with instructions for doing something. The word project has several meanings. It comes from the Latin word *proectus*, formed by *proicere*, which means “forward” and *iacere*, which means “to throw”. For example, in engineering and architecture, projects are a collection of data, plans, and precise calculations designed to provide information about what the work should look like and how much it should cost.

This is a systematic integrated process aimed at modernizing certain areas of human life and activity. Currently, technical projects are in the greatest demand because they help improve the quality of life of the inhabitants of our planet. Taking into account the need for special projects to implement projects and the fact that the methods for solving the task may depend on various parameters, the following components are distinguished:

- ✧ major plan (setting goals and objectives);
- ✧ solution resources;
- ✧ results.

This concept of the project demonstrates the complexity and multifaceted nature of its structure. It is capable of making significant changes in the lives of individuals and the entire country. The results of its implementation can be abstract or specific, necessary for a particular region.

Nowadays, project work has become a form of work not only in large firms and industrial companies, but also in medical and educational institutions. Primary educational organizations and schools are offering interesting projects that identify and develop the creative abilities of each child, that is, fully meet the requirements of new educational standards.

The uniqueness of any project creates certain challenges and considerations when planning it in advance. It is often difficult for the author (creative team) to immediately predict how they

will achieve the planned results. Therefore, the results of the activity can be not only services or products, but also a certain experience that the developers can use in their further activities.

Any organization can use this form of work, involving from 2-3 people to several thousand researchers. Projects are increasingly common not only in industrial organizations, but also in educational and medical institutions. For example, involving children in extracurricular activities has become an interesting and timely part of the work of schools. In the theory and practice of educational design, various types of projects are distinguished.

Depending on the number of students involved, they can be individual, paired, and group.

An individual project is an effective way to organize independent research activities, taking into account the student's personal interests, ensuring the realization of his creative potential, achieving success, and the need for self-affirmation;

Pair and group projects are not without their developmental potential, allowing you to take into account the individual characteristics of students when distributing tasks, as well as teach students the ability to coordinate their efforts in the process of jointly solving complex creative tasks.

By the nature and priority methods of search activities, research, creative and information projects are divided into:

By their nature, **scientific projects** resemble scientific research, are subject to its logic, and include the following:

development of the problem, object and topic, the purpose of the study, the hypothesis, the task, the methodology and method of studying the problem; collecting and analyzing information, conducting experiments, developing practical recommendations, etc. Projects of this type are often developed as part of term and diploma design;

Creative projects are aimed at developing new original ideas presented in a creative way, products of joint activities (creative report, exhibition, design project for production facilities, video, printed materials - book, almanac, computer dictionary, computer program, etc.). Main work methods: "brainstorming", "sequential", creative group style (laboratory, design bureau, workshop, editorial office, etc.);

Information projects are aimed at collecting information necessary for the educational process or other clients. Project development involves searching and searching for information in various sources: monographs, journal articles, newspaper publications, electronic databases, using sociological surveys.

DISCUSSION

The results of the project are selected, analyzed, summarized, systematized, and presented in a specific form as information - a booklet, collage, publication, or web page.

Depending on the scope of the project developed, projects can be divided into types such as production (technical) and social. In addition, they can be effective and social if they solve problems that are important for improving the social aspects of production (communication, management, improving living conditions, etc.).

Depending on the nature of the problems developed, they are divided into: *theoretical* and *practice-oriented projects*. Thus, students develop their own educational concepts in creative groups based on the approaches to education taught in the history of pedagogy. A variety of practical nature is the development of a project aimed at solving a specific practical problem, ordered by a college or special teacher (methodological project). These types can be successfully

combined in one project. Such as, a theoretical project conducted in the “Management” subject and aimed at studying and analyzing the organizational culture of an enterprise is carried out simultaneously with the preparation of the video “Specialization of a Store and the Organizational Culture of a Trading Company”, which is used as teaching material in several subjects at the same time.

We can divide the project into the following, depending on the academic disciplines being developed:

- ✧ *thematic projects* are carried out within the framework of one academic discipline;
- ✧ *interdisciplinary projects* are carried out in the process of studying a specific course, but are based on the active use of materials from other disciplines;
- ✧ *Thematic projects* are not only related to a specific discipline, but are also carried out, as a rule, outside the framework of a specific academic discipline.

Interdisciplinary projects ensure the active and effective activity of students in the process of training a specialist with knowledge and skills acquired in the study of various disciplines, based on systematization, integration and comprehensive use. The duration and term of projects may be as follows:

- ✧ *short period* is developed in several classes or during independent work among students;
- ✧ *medium-term* - from a week to a month;
- ✧ *long-term*- developed from one to several months.

Short-term projects are mainly used in the study of a specific subject, while long-term projects include course and diploma design.

Often, students’ educational projects are complex and combine several types. The combination of research and practice-oriented projects, individual and group forms of organizing work on them allows not only to master research skills, but also to master systematic methods for solving production problems based on the cooperation of their individual projects.

What is an educational project? How does the process of preparing educational projects work?

To create a project, the pedagogues:

- create project;
- step-by-step explanation of the process;
- clearly defining the goal;
- identifying tasks that are appropriate for the goal;
- shaping the content of educational material;
- developing a system of questions and tasks;
- justify the methodological structure of the process or event;
- It is necessary to have skills and qualifications such as diagnosing the level of knowledge of a student and assessing his level of education.

Designing the educational process - developing a project (scheme) for the effective organization of a particular educational process, taking into account all factors.

Principles of designing the educational process:

1) the effectiveness of the design of the educational process is ensured by the appropriate coverage of all components (technological process, technological process management, tools, information, socio-economic support) in the project;

- 2) educational technology is selected depending on the individual characteristics of students;
- 3) project strategies are selected according to the individual style of the educator;
- 4) the quality of the design depends on the extent of feedback (between the teacher and the student), the content of the design, and the effectiveness of all factors.

When designing educational processes, it is advisable to correctly determine the content of education, educational goals, and expected results, correctly select educational methods, forms, and tools, develop clear criteria for assessing children's knowledge, skills, and competencies in advance, and pay attention to their correct implementation and coordination within the time allotted for the lesson.

The main stage of preparation for training sessions is the design of the training process. This process is organized in the following stages:

1. Determine the purpose and outcome of the training.
2. Develop control tasks and assessment criteria.
3. Select educational resources.
4. Determine the teaching and learning strategy.
5. Select the type of training.
6. Develop a technological map of the training.

Technological map (in pedagogy) - a document containing all the necessary information and instructions provided to educators performing a pedagogical process or providing technical maintenance to a specific facility. Modeling is also usually used in the design of the educational process.

A model is a simplified, scaled-down (enlarged) or similar copy of a real, actually existing object.

Modeling is the creation of a model that fully reflects the general essence of a phenomenon, process or system.

The following models are used in the learning process:

1. Educational models (used in the educational process; instructional tools, visual aids, simulators, educational programs).
2. Experimental models (used in conducting scientific, practical experiments; an enlarged or reduced copy of the object being designed).
3. Scientific and technical models (used in studying processes and phenomena; devices, devices, tools, equipment and mechanisms).
4. Game models (used to develop skills and competencies by performing various actions by the object in various situations; computer, sports, economic, military, business games, etc.).
5. Imitation models (used not only to accurately reflect real reality to one degree or another, but also to imitate it; various simulators, mechanisms that serve to perform practical actions).

Today, in the educational process, attention is paid to the preparation of various educational projects by children, which serves as the basis for achieving efficiency in the pedagogical process.

In the direction of engineering based on STEAM educational technology, that is, in the development of engineering and technical creativity, it is advisable to work on small projects with children of primary age.

CONCLUSION. Designing in STEAM educational technology is an important process that increases the effectiveness of educational activities and requires the professional skills of the

teacher in designing, modeling, and designing the pedagogical process. Also, creating and implementing small projects in educational activities in primary education organizations is one of the current issues today.

In the design process of STEAM educational technology, modeling, and implementing targeted work based on a plan are necessary, in which it is necessary to work together between the educator and the students.

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